

REN+HOMES

Brand Identity guidelines

V 1.0

+ *Concept*

The main goal of the *RENplusHOMES* project is to tackle the sustainable transition by **reducing carbon emissions, resource scarcity and energy poverty** thanks to **energy positive homes**.

The visual identity is designed to reflect its core aspects:
Essential - Energy - Recycling - Positive - Technology

The logo icon is made up by three different elements. The “R”, that represents the brand, is trapped under a house roof, from which a “+” figure stands out and connects the two shapes. It is a **very clear and simple image** that, thanks to its bright colours and free spaces, is universally readable and easily recognisable.

+ Brand Personality

+ *Main Logo*

REN+HOMES

+ *Horizontal Logo*

+ Main Logo On Dark Background

REN+HOMES

+ Horizontal Logo
On Dark Background

+ *Monochrome Logo*

+ Safe Area

+ Icon

+ Colour Palette

Enlightened Blue

R	0	C	100
G	67	M	30
B	255	Y	0
		K	10

Deep Blue

R	0	C	100
G	16	M	80
B	22	Y	0
		K	30

Cloudy White

R	236	C	10
G	242	M	3
B	246	Y	3
		K	0

Infinite Black

R	0	C	0
G	0	M	0
B	0	Y	0
		K	100

Each colour has its own CMYK variant.

Pay attention to the colour properties of logos and elements when using them.

+ Texture

Never use this texture underneath a paragraph text.
It could create confusion and make the text unreadable.

+ Typography

Ellograph CF Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789 (!#€%&/.|*~?;:)

Ellograph CF Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789 (!#€%&/.|*~?;:)

Ellograph CF Thin

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789 (!#€%&/.|*~?;:)

Ellograph CF Bold Italic

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789 (!#€%&/.|*~?;:)

Ellograph CF Regular Italic

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789 (!#€%&/.|*~?;:)

Ellograph CF Thin Italic

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789 (!#€%&/.|*~?;:)

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The rules specified in this document are to be considered guidelines to better understand the project and to look at when designing something new, evolving its identity, or even when breaking the rules.

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